
ERS Scatterometer SIR-Enhanced *EASE-Grid 2.0* Radar Backscatter

Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
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Cover Image

Color montage of morning overpass AMSR2 horizontally-polarized 36 GHz passive microwave brightness temperatures, 29–30 June, 2003, by M. J. Brodzik, National Snow and Ice Data Center.

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1 Revision History

Table 1: *ATBD Revision History*

Revision	Date	Purpose
1.0	2024-12-25	Initial Version

Table 2: *Data Set Revision History*

Revision	Date	Purpose
1.0	2023-01-05	Initial Data Release

2 Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 3: List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

ADEOS	Advanced Earth Observing Satellite
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
AVE	weighted AVeraging image formation algorithm
BYU	Brigham Young University
CDR	Climate Data Record
CETB	Calibrated Passive Microwave Daily EASE-Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature
CF	Climate and Forecast Metadata Conventions
DAAC	Distributed Active Archive Center
dB	decibel ($10 \log_{10}$)
DIB	Drop-In-the-Bucket averaging (used to produce GRD products)
DOY	Day Of Year
E2N	EASE-Grid 2.0, Northern Hemisphere Projection
E2S	EASE-Grid 2.0, Southern Hemisphere Projection
E2T	EASE-Grid 2.0, Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical Projection
EASE-Grid	Equal-Area Scalable Earth Grid (Original Definition)
EASE-Grid 2.0	Equal-Area Scalable Earth Grid Version 2.0
EASE2-M	EASE-Grid 2.0, Mid- and Low-Latitude Cylindrical Projection
EASE2-N	EASE-Grid 2.0, Northern Hemisphere Projection
EASE2-S	EASE-Grid 2.0, Southern Hemisphere Projection
EASE2-T	EASE-Grid 2.0, Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical Projection
EOSDIS	Earth Observing System Data and Information System
ERS	Earth Remote Sensing
ESA	European Space Agency
ESCAT	ERS Scatterometer
ESDR	Earth System Data Record
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FCDR	Fundamental Climate Data Record
GHz	GigaHertz
GRD	(Drop-In-the-Bucket) Gridding Method
LFM	linear frequency modulation
LTOD	local-time-of-day
MEaSURES	Making Earth System Data Records for Use in Research Environments
MRF	Measurement Response Function
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

Acronyms and Abbreviations

NSIDC	National Snow and Ice Data Center
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
PRF	Pulse Repetition Frequency
PSRF	Pixel Spatial Response Function
SCP	Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder
SDR	Sensor Data Record
Sigma-0	normalized radar cross section or backscatter (σ^0)
SIR	Scatterometer Image Reconstruction
SIRF	Scatterometer Image Reconstruction with median Filtering
VV	Vertical-polarization transmit, Vertical-polarization receive

3 Purpose of this Document

This Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) describes a CETB-compatible radar backscatter product created from the ESA Earth Remote Sensing (ERS) Scatterometer (ES-CAT) 5.225 GHz radar observations collected between 1992–2001.

ESCAT (Attema, 1991a) collected nominally ~ 50 km resolution normalized radar cross section, or (σ^o) from 3 different azimuth angles over a 500 km wide swath. ESCAT employed three long, fan-beam antennas with narrow beamwidths, see Fig. 1. Along-beam resolution was achieved using 5 ms linear frequency modulated transmit pulses and FFT-based processing. Nominally 25 km σ^o measurements were reported by combining FFT bins. The individual beams were reported in the highest resolution data, termed ‘SZF’. The SZF bins extended beyond the nominal swath width to lower and higher incidence angles. The calibration this extended swath is not considered as accurate as those over the nominal wind swath. The σ^o measurements collected by each beam in sequence span from low ($\sim 15^\circ$) incidence angles near the nadir track to larger (up to 60°) at the outer edge of the swath. The multiple beams provided azimuth diversity of the σ^o measurements, which is required to retrieve the surface wind (Attema, 1991a)(Ulaby and Long, 2014)(Naderi et al., 1991)

While designed and optimized for ocean observation, ESCAT also collected σ^o measurements over land and ice. The observed σ^o depends on the surface roughness, geometry, and dielectric constant. These depend on geophysical parameters of interest such as surface freeze/thaw state, snow and ice structure, moisture content, and vegetation characteristics, among others (Ulaby and Long, 2014). The ESCAT data set provides a unique “snapshot” of the Earth during its mission lifetime (1992–2001).

The ESCAT radar backscatter (*ESCAT*) product exploits the ESCAT measurements to create a unique backscatter image data set that captures the state of the Earth during the ESCAT mission (1992-2001). To exploit this data, we employ image reconstruction techniques to create conventional resolution and enhanced resolution ESCAT radar images from the measurements. The new data set is provided to the science community to support cryosphere and climate studies.

Figure 1: ESCAT observation swath. Nominally 50 km σ^0 measurements are collected over a nominal 500 km wide swath. The scatterometer antennas have three narrow footprints at azimuth angles of 45°, 90°, and 135° (Attema, 1991a).

4 Gridded and SIR-Enhanced Product Description

4.1 Product Description

The *ESCAT* product includes Level 1 gridded, twice-daily, radar backscatter data collected at 5.3 GHz with vertical transmit-vertical receive [VV] polarization. Data are gridded to the EASE-Grid 2.0 Azimuthal and Cylindrical projections (Brodzik et al., 2012)(Brodzik et al., 2014), at two spatial resolutions, as described below. The *ESCAT* product is archived and distributed by the National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center (<https://nsidc.org/data/NSIDC-TBD/versions/1>).

Input data for the *ESCAT* v1.0 product are the *ESCAT* Wind/Sigma0 files obtained through from ESA during the flight mission. Using the quality flags in the input data, only measurements not flagged as "bad" are included in *ESCAT* product. The data coverage is global for the period beginning in Jan. 1992 through the through early 2001. No calibration corrections were applied to the data.

4.2 ESCAT Instrument

ESCAT flew on two satellites, ERS-1 launched in 1991 and ERS-2 launched in 1995. The two sensors simultaneously operated for nearly two months in 1995 before ERS-1 was shut-down. The ERS satellites flew in a sun-synchronous 785 km circular polar orbits with an orbit inclination angle of 98.52°.

The *ESCAT* instrument is described in Attema (1991b). *ESCAT* is a fan-beam Doppler range-gate scatterometer that uses pulse-compression to achieve along-beam resolution (Ulaby and Long, 2014). The *ESCAT* instrument employs three 3 m long fan-beam antennas deployed to provide three VV polarized azimuth angle observations on one side of the spacecraft, see Fig. 1. Along-track resolution is provided by the narrow beamwidth of the antenna beams and the pulse timing. Along-beam resolution is provided via pulse compression of a 10 us linear frequency modulated (LFM) pulse, illustrated in Fig. 2. Note that synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and scatterometer share a transmitter and receiver, which means that the scatterometer does not collect data during SAR imaging. This produces systematic gaps in *ESCAT* coverage.

Multiple pulses are processed and summed into a single measurement. The SRF of an individual SZF σ^o measurements is defined by the range-gate timing bin limits and the antenna gain pattern¹. The SRF, which varies for each measurement and beams, defines the intrinsic resolution of the measurement (Long and Stroeve, 2011).

¹Note that while a radiometer's footprint is defined by the antenna pattern, the radar footprint is defined by the antenna pattern squared due to the two-way travel of the signal from radar to the surface and back, by range-gate timing, and by signal processing of the signal (Ulaby and Long, 2014).

Figure 2: *ESCAT measurement theory illustrations. Intersection of the fan-beam footprint and isorange lines used to define the along-beam resolution. (Ulaby and Long, 2014)*

ESCAT collected return echo power measurements, which were converted into σ^o using the radar equation (EUMETSAT, 2022)(Ulaby and Long, 2014). The σ^o value depends on the surface roughness, geometry, and dielectric constant (Ulaby and Long, 2014). In processing the ESCAT data, the raw backscatter observations were resampled into a windowed 25 km along-track/cross-track wind vector cell (WVC) grid illustrated in Fig. 3 (Attema, 1991b). This regridding processing step severely limits the enhanced resolution processing possible with ESCAT data since the raw measurement locations are somewhat variable with the v

As described below, from these σ^o measurements global images were created by (1) DIB gridding of the σ^o measurements onto a 25 km grid, and (2) applying the SIR algorithm to enhance the effective resolution of the data by exploiting the irregular patterns of measurement locations and signal oversampling from overlaps in adjacent footprints and overlapping swaths. The SIR images are reported on a 6.25 km grid.

4.3 Grid Spatial Extent

Azimuthal *ESCAT* grids extend to the full Northern (EASE2-N) and Southern (EASE2-S) hemispheres (Fig. 4), as described in Brodzik et al. (2012, 2014). The spatial extent of the equal-area cylindrical projections (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6) is defined to match the extent of compatible grids favored by two user communities: (1) the Mid-Latitude (EASE2-M) grid, extending to $\pm 85.0445664^\circ$ latitude, has been adopted by the SMAP user community. And, (2) the Temperate and Tropical (EASE2-T) grid, limited to latitudes equatorward of $\pm 67.1^\circ$, is consistent with the original CETB products defined for similar scanning radiometers (Brodzik et al., 2021). See Appendix A Table 6 for grid specifications.

Figure 3: *ESCAT* wind vector cell (WVC) grid illustration. A particular WVC is highlighted in black.

4.4 Grid Spatial Resolution

ESCAT grid resolutions are defined relative to a 25 km base resolution, i.e., 25 km and 6.25 km MEaSURES CETB data products (Brodzik et al., 2021). Nested resolutions relative to the CETB 25 km base grids are defined using exact divisors of 2, as illustrated in Figure 7. *ESCAT* projection extents, dimensions and grid cell size details are included in Appendix A. Grids used for *ESCAT* processing are included in Table 4.

Table 4: *ESCAT* EASE-Grid 2.0 base grids produced by the projection and reconstruction algorithm. See Section 5 for GRD and SIR reconstruction details.

EASE2-M	EASE2-N	EASE2-S	EASE2-T
n/a	25km (GRD)	25km (GRD)	25km (GRD)
n/a	6.25km (AVE/SIR)	6.25km (AVE/SIR)	6.25km (AVE/SIR)

4.5 Data Products

The *ESCAT* product at the NSIDC DAAC covers the period beginning 1 Jan. 1992. through early 2001. No calibration corrections were applied to the data. In creating a time series, a “moving average” approach was used with overlapping imaging periods that start on a mission day and extend through the desired 6-, 18-day period (or to the end of the mission, whichever comes first). 6-day and 18-day images start three mission day. Table 5

Figure 4: Northern and Southern EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents. The land-ocean mask from Brodzik and Knowles (2011).

Figure 5: Cylindrical EASE-Grid 2.0 projection extents. Full extent coverage is EASE2-M, with horizontal red lines delineating the smaller latitudinal extent of the EASE2-T grid. The land-ocean mask is from Brodzik and Knowles (2011).

Figure 6: Relationship of EASE-Grid 2.0 cylindrical projection extents. The EASE2-T extent is defined for compatibility with the CETB products. (Difference in latitudinal extent is exaggerated, see Fig. 5 for actual difference in projected extent (Brodzik et al., 2021)).

Figure 7: CETB nested grids based on a 25 km base resolution. Only 25 km and 6.25 km divisions are used in ESCAT products (Long et al., 2019).

summarizes the available *ESCAT* products, which are all in CETB-standard EASE-2 Grid projections.

Table 5: Available *ESCAT* image products. *ESCAT* operates at only VV polarization.

Image Period	Algorithm	Pix. Res. (km)	Regions*	Size† N/S/T (MB)
6,18	GRD	25	N,S,T	3/3/5
6,18	AVE	6.25	N,S,T	46/46/85
6,18	SIR	6.25	N,S,T	46/46/85

* Region code: N=Northern Hemisphere, S=Southern Hemisphere, T=Global

† Uncompressed size. Compressed sizes vary but are 30-40% of compressed sizes.

5 Algorithm Description

5.1 Background

The *effective resolution* of an image is defined by the *pixel spatial response function* (PSRF), where the effective resolution is given by the dimension(s) of the one-half power (3-dB) extent of the PSRF. In contrast, the *measurement response function* (MRF) describes the spatial characteristics of the *individual* measurements that were combined to create the image. For a radar, the MRF depends on the two-way antenna gain pattern, the scan geometry, and the signal processing. For both radars and radiometers, the PSRF depends on the MRF and the image formation algorithm. In a linear image formation algorithm, the reported pixel value consists of the weighted sum of nearby measurements. In this case the PSRF is then the normalized weighted sum of the measurement MRF functions, including their spatial offset from the center of the pixel.

The spacing of pixels is termed the “pixel posting” or the “posting resolution”. In creating the *ESCAT* backscatter image product, multiple measurements from different passes are combined into single pixel values. The resulting image pixels have an effective resolution slightly coarser than the posting resolution since (1) the measurements are not all centered the same, and (2) their MRFs can extend outside of the pixel area. The PSRF provides the tool for defining the effective pixel resolution (Long and Brodzik, 2016a). In order to be compatible with the CETB data set, two posting resolutions are considered: 25 km and 6.25 km, see Fig. 8. The former is used only for gridded (DIB) products while the latter is used for enhanced resolution products such as AVE and SIR.

5.2 *ESCAT* Backscatter Image Products

The *ESCAT* backscatter products include both low-noise (low-resolution) coarse resolution GRD images and higher-noise (enhanced) fine-resolution (SIR) images. The various products have their advantages and disadvantages. Multiple image types allow users the flexibility of choosing the appropriate images for their research application.

To create radar CETB-compatible products, different approaches are used for each resolution. Because the sensor was not designed as an imager, there are gaps between the measurements that must be filled by combining multiple passes over an extended imaging period. As a result of the 4 day near-repeat cycle, multiple imaging periods are defined²: 6 day and ‘8 day. These provide a user-selectable tradeoff between temporal resolution, spatial resolution, and noise.

For GRD images, the source backscatter measurements are gridded onto a 25 km grid using DIB techniques. In this approach, all the measurements whose center location falls

²Ideally, an 8 day period would be included to improve azimuth sampling with an LTOD, but this was not done due to computational limitations.

Figure 8: Conceptual illustration of coarse 25 km (left) vs. high resolution (right) pixels. The ellipses represent the individual MRFs of the measurements (the actual shapes are more complicated than this.) DIB is used for GRD images while AVE and SIR are used for high resolution images.

within a grid element are averaged into the reported value. For the 6.25 km product, the source measurements are processed using the the first iteration of the SIR algorithm, termed ‘AVE’. AVE images are weighted averages of the measurements which cover the pixel, where the weighting is based on the measurement MRF, which varies from measurement to measurement. Along with each measurement’s MRF, the SIR algorithm exploits the irregular patterns of the measurement locations and signal oversampling from overlaps in adjacent footprints and overlapping passes. Table 5 summarizes the image product types.

5.3 Radar Spatial Response and Image Reconstruction

The effective spatial resolution of an image product is determined by the MRF of the sensor and by the image formation algorithm used. As previously noted, the MRF is determined by the antenna gain pattern, the scan geometry (notably the antenna scan angle), and the signal processing, see (Long et al., 1993, Long, 2017, Lindsley et al., 2016). The goal in forming a σ^o image is to estimate the backscatter properties of the surface from noisy measurements that employ (possibly variable) MRFs that sample the surface. Though simple to implement, DIB techniques ignore the MRF, which limits their effective resolution. Reconstruction techniques that use the MRF can provide much finer effective resolution.

Reconstruction processing techniques effectively assume the underlying signal (the backscatter) being sampled is band-limited, which is the only consistent assumption possible with sampled data (Long and Brodzik, 2016b, Long and Franz, 2016b). For reconstruction, the backscatter at each point of a fine-scale pixel grid is estimated, producing a backscatter

image or map. While the image is generated on a regular grid, the measurement locations and MRF are not aligned with the grid, and so the measurements form an irregular sampling pattern, which can complicate signal reconstruction. Many commonly used image formation algorithms either ignore this (as is done in DIB) or attempt to interpolate or distance-weight the measurements values. In using image reconstruction, we avoid these ad hoc, non-optimal approaches and explicitly compute the MRF of each measurement as part of the reconstruction process. This is computationally intense, but provides the best possible image construction. The remainder of this section outlines this process.

An individual scatterometer backscatter measurement z_i can be modeled as the integral of the product of the MRF and the surface backscatter, i.e.,

$$z_i = \iint \text{MRF}_i(x, y; pp) \sigma^o(x, y, \theta, \phi_i, t, pp) dx dy + \text{noise} \quad (1)$$

where $\text{MRF}_i(x, y; pp)$ is the spatial MRF of the i^{th} measurement at x, y and the surface σ^o depends on spatial location x, y , incidence angle θ , azimuth angle ϕ , time t , and polarization pp , i.e.,

$$\text{MRF}_i(x, y; pp) = \iint \frac{G_a^2(x, y; pp) G_p(x, y; pp)}{R^4(x, y)}. \quad (2)$$

where

$$X = \iint \frac{G_a^2(x, y; pp) G_p(x, y; pp)}{R^4(x, y)} dx dy. \quad (3)$$

where $G_a(x, y; pp)$ is the effective two-way antenna gain at the surface at (x, y) for polarization pp , $G_p(x, y; pp)$ is the processor gain, and $R(x, y)$ is the slant range from the radar to the surface. Note that the measurement is an average of σ^o in spatial coordinates as well as in azimuth and incidence angles.

Eq. 1 is discretized on the imaging grid to become

$$z_i = \sum_{j \in \text{image}} h_{ij} a_j + \text{noise} \quad (4)$$

where a_j is the backscatter at the center of the j^{th} pixel at (x_l, y_k) and $h_{ij} = \text{MRF}(x_l, y_k; \phi_i)$ is the discretely sampled MRF for the i -th measurement evaluated at the j -th pixel center where h_{ij} is normalized so that $\sum_j h_{ij} = 1$. In practice, the MRF is negligible some distance from the measurement center, so the sums need only be computed over a small area around the pixel. Ignoring the noise, Eq. 4 can be written as the matrix equation

$$\vec{Z} = \mathbf{H} \vec{a} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{H} contains the sampled MRF for each measurement and \vec{Z} and \vec{a} are vectors composed of the measurements z_i and a_j , respectively. Even for small images, \mathbf{H} is large and

sparse, and may be over-determined or under-determined depending on the number and locations of the measurements. Reconstruction of the surface σ^o is equivalent to inverting Eq. 5.

The iterative SIR algorithm (Early and Long, 2001)(Long et al., 1993) is a particular reconstruction algorithm that is specifically developed for scatterometer image formation. SIR approximates a maximum-entropy solution to an under-determined equation and a least-squares solution to an over-determined system. The first iteration of SIR is termed 'AVE' (for weighted AVErage) and provides a simple reconstruction estimate that is refined in later SIR iterations. The AVE estimate of the j -th pixel is given by

$$a_j = \frac{\sum_i h_{ij} z_i}{\sum_i h_{ij}} \quad (6)$$

where the sums are over all measurements that have non-negligible MRF at the pixel. The SIR iteration begins with an initial image a_j^0 whose pixels are set to the AVE values defined in Eq. 6. Thereafter, the iterative equation for single-variate SIR is given by

$$a_j^{k+1} = \frac{\sum_i u_{ij}^k h_{ij}}{\sum_i h_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

where

$$u_{ij}^k = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{1}{2p_i^k} \left(1 - \frac{1}{d_i^k} \right) + \frac{1}{a_j^k d_i^k} \right]^{-1} & d_i^k \geq 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} p_i^k (1 - d_i^k) + a_j^k d_i^k & d_i^k < 1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$d_i^k = \left(\frac{z_i}{p_i^k} \right)^\lambda \quad (9)$$

where $d_i^k = (s_i/p_i^k)^\lambda$ with $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$. The factor d_i^k is the square root of the ratio of a measurement to its forward projection at the k^{th} iteration. The update term u_{ij}^k is a non-linear function of both d_i^k and the previous image a_j^k . The sigmoid-like non-linearity in Eq. 8 constrains the amount of change permitted during any one iteration, thereby minimizing the effects of noise (Long et al., 1993). Though not used in this paper, a spatial median filter can be applied to the image between iterations to further reduce the noise (Long et al., 1993).

For scatterometers, SIR is implemented in dB (Long, 2017)(Early and Long, 2001)(Long et al., 1993); i.e., the computation is done on $10 \log_{10}(z_i)$ rather than on the linear-space value z_i as done in the radiometer version of SIR (Long and Brodzik, 2016a)(Long and Daum, 1998). In considering the differences between linear and dB processing, recall the well-known fact that computing the arithmetic mean of values in dB is equivalent to computing $10 \log_{10}$ of the geometric mean of the linear-space values (Wikipedia, 2016). With

the measurements in dB, the reconstruction processing can be viewed as a form of weighted geometric mean filtering. Since it has been found that geometric mean filters are better at reducing Gaussian-type noise and preserving linear features than (linear) arithmetic mean filters (Pitas and Venetsanopoulos, 1986), some performance advantage to dB processing is expected and observed (Long, 2017). The linear and dB computations yield similar, but slightly different results, due to the varying signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the measurements and limited signal dynamic range (Long, 2017).

In practice, since the σ^o measurements are quite noisy, attempting full image reconstruction can produce excessive noise enhancement. In general, more iterations improve the signal and resolution, but also increase the noise level. To reduce noise enhancement and resulting artifacts, regularization can be employed, at the expense of resolution (Long and Franz, 2016a)(Early and Long, 2001)(Long et al., 1993)(Long, 2017). Regularization is a smoothing constraint introduced in an inverse problem to prevent extreme values or over-fitting. Regularization results in partial or incomplete reconstruction of the signal (Long and Franz, 2016a). It also creates a trade off between signal reconstruction accuracy and noise enhancement (Early and Long, 2001). SIR includes regularization achieved by prematurely terminating the iteration. Based on simulations and confirmed by analysis of actual data, 20-30 iterations provides a nice tradeoff result for ESCAT (Early and Long, 2001). The results can be improved by median filtering the images between iterations. This latter variation is termed "SIRF", and is employed (only) for ESCAT data (Long et al., 1993). We note that for a noisy sensor such as a scatterometer, the results are not particularly sensitive to the precise value chosen; hence, a fixed value can be selected. Selection of the number of iterations is based on simulation, see (Early and Long, 2001), (Long et al., 1993) and (Long, 2017). For this product, a fixed (30) number of SIR iterations is employed.

As previously noted, the goal of image reconstruction is to estimate the surface σ^o from the sensor σ^o measurements. Measurements from multiple orbit passes over a narrow local time window are combined. When multiple measurements are combined, the resulting images represent a temporal average of the measurements over the averaging period. There is an implicit assumption that the surface characteristics remain constant over the imaging period. For both conventional-resolution (GRD) and enhanced-resolution (SIR) images.

The radar backscatter of a natural surface is a strong function of the state of the water it contains, i.e., frozen or thawed. As a result of the sun-synchronous orbit geometry, the radar observations at a given location on the earth fall within two narrow diurnal windows. At the equator, these correspond to the ascending and descending orbit passes. This can be exploited to provide twice-daily sampling. Thus, ESCAT images on the cylindrical EASE-Grid 2.0 projections are separated by ascending and descending passes. A separate image ("both") product is also made that combines both which achieves between spatial coverage at the expense of temporal resolution.

5.4 Sample Data

Figures 9–11 present examples of 18-day product images for each polarization and region where all passes (‘both’) within the imaging period are combined. Swath-like artifacts over the oceans are the result of significant temporal variation of surface σ^o due to wind changes during the imaging interval. Over the ocean high winds correspond to higher average σ^o values while low winds correspond to low wind speeds. Since the measurements are averaged over multiple days and the wind is highly variable over this time period, the ocean values are not considered particularly useful. Land and ice backscatter is much more stable and is the focus of this product.

Figure 9 compares the GRD, AVE, and SIR images of an area in northeast Greenland. Note the improved contrast and resolution of the SIR images relative to GRD, with AVE falling between the two. Additional data visualizations are provided in later sections.

Figure 9: Visualizations of examples of 6-day (DOY 1-6, 2000) ESCAT-A (left) A (σ^o at 40° incidence angle) and (right) B (slope of σ^o versus incidence angle in dB/deg at 40° incidence angle) polarizations. Images have been reduced in resolution for presentation here.

Figure 10: Visualizations of examples of 6-day (DOY 3-6, 2009) ESCAT-A (left) A (σ^o at 40° incidence angle) and (right) B (slope of σ^o versus incidence angle in dB/deg at 40° incidence angle) polarizations. Images have been reduced in resolution for presentation here.

Figure 11: Visualizations of examples of 18-day (DOY 1-18, 2000) ESCAT-A (top) A (σ^o at 40° incidence angle) and (bottom) B (slope of σ^o versus incidence angle in dB/deg at 40° incidence angle) polarizations. Images have been reduced in resolution for presentation here.

Figure 12: Zoom-in of West Antarctica *A* images to compare (upper left) GRD 25 km pixel, (upper right) AVE 6.25 km pixel, and (lower left) SIR 6.25 km pixel images. Data from from data 180-197, 1998.

Figure 13: Zoom-in of West Antarctica B images to compare (upper left) GRD 25 km pixel, (upper right) AVE 6.25 km pixel, and (lower left) SIR 6.25 km pixel images. Data from from data 180-197, 1998.

6 Measurement Modeling

To dive deeper into the backscatter data and the performance of the imaging algorithms, a coastal region is employed to visualize the differences between the products at fine resolution, see Figs. 12 and 13, which shows west Antarctica. Pixelization and coverage edge artifacts are evident in the 25 km GRD with slightly finer resolution and higher contrast in the SIR image. The AVE image is smoothed compared to the other images. Note that because ESCAT only observes to a single side of the nadir track, there is generally a large no-coverage area over the South Pole. However, for a short experimental period, the spacecraft was “flipped around” in order to image to the other side, so some data was collected near the pole.

6.1 Incidence Angle Effects

Over natural surfaces σ° depends on the measurement incidence angle. Since ESCAT is a fan-beam system, it collects σ° measurements over a range of incidence angles ranging from about 15° to 60° . The variation in incidence angle must be accounted for when combining multiple measurements. The incidence angle normalization $\gamma^\circ = \sigma^\circ / \cos \theta$ where θ is the incidence angle is sometimes used. However, the slope of this correction is strictly downward and since upward slopes are observed in some areas, this normalization is not used. Further, this normalization is based on specific backscatter model which does not apply to all natural surface. Instead, following prior investigators, see Long et al. (1993), Long and Miller (2023), and references therein, a linear slope is used that is centered at 40° , i.e., σ° (in dB) as a function of incidence angle is modelled according to

$$\sigma^\circ(\text{in dB}) = A + B(\theta - 40^\circ) \quad (10)$$

where A is σ° at 40° incidence angle; B is the slope of σ° versus incidence angle θ . The /prod product is defined by images of A and B estimated from the σ° values collected from each pixel. Note that this requires multiple σ° measurements at different incidence angles in order to estimate A and B , i.e., at each pixel, the model parameters A (the mean σ°), B (the normalized slope of σ° versus incidence angle) are estimated from the backscatter measurements on a pixel by pixel basis. In creating the ESCAT product only from measurements with incidence angle greater than 20° are used. When there is inadequate incidence angle diversity at a pixel, a fixed value of $B = -0.14$ dB/deg is used to infer an A value for that pixel. This occurs most frequently in locations with missing coverage due to ERS-SAR operation, notably over Europe and calibration areas in South America and Africa.

Figure 14 illustrates ESCAT σ° versus incidence angles for several arbitrarily selected locations for July 2000. Measurements are from 2° longitude by 1° latitude boxes with corners as indicated in the plot titles. Note the linear dependence of σ° in dB with incidence angles for incidence angles greater than 15° . A linear fit of σ° in dB versus incidence angle

Figure 14: Plots of ESCAT-measured σ^o versus incidence angles over a 28-day period in July 2000 for different areas of the globe. Each plot shows values over 2° longitude by 1° latitude box. See text.

is shown, with the coefficients from Eq. 10 shown. Measurements with incidence angles less than 5° were not included in the linear fit.

Note that there is a trade off between the imaging time period and the spatial resolution. Short time periods provide better temporal resolution for tracking sea ice motion and rapid freeze-thaw events. However, short time periods provide inadequate coverage to reliably estimate the incidence angle variation. The imaging intervals are chosen to overlap by 50% days so they act like a long moving average filter. Shorter imaging intervals provide finer temporal resolution at the expense of reduced spatial coverage/resolution, including possible spatial artifacts in the reconstruction. These negative effects are reduced for longer imaging intervals.

Note that a particular σ° observation is an average of σ° in spatial coordinates as well as in azimuth and incidence angles. Within a single measurement the azimuth angle span and incidence angle spans within a single measurement are very small ($\ll 1^\circ$) and can be neglected. The roll off of σ° versus incidence angle, slightly biases the integrated measurement toward smaller incidence angles. This effect is neglected. Similarly, the variation of σ° within a particular slice footprint is neglected.

6.2 Data Volume

Table 5 summarizes available CETB *ESCAT* radar products, which are all in CETB-standard EASE-2 Grid projections. In this table, “days” refers to the length of time used for image formation. Imaging periods overlap, with a new image started each three day period. Individual file sizes vary due to internal file compression for each image type. See Section 4.5 for access details.

7 Acknowledgements

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8 References

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Appendices

A ESCAT Projections and Grids

Table 6: ESCAT 25 km product EASE-Grid 2.0 projections and grid dimensions, produced for compatibility with CETB ESDR data products (Brodzik et al., 2021).

Name	Projection	Resolution (km)	Cols	Rows	Latitude Extent	Longitude Extent
EASE2-T25km	Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical	25.025 260 00	1388	540	$\pm 67.057 640 6^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-T3.125km	Temperate and Tropical Cylindrical	3.128 157 50	11 104	4320	$\pm 67.057 640 6^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-N25km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	25.0	720	720	$0^\circ-90^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-N3.125km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	3.125	5760	5760	$0^\circ-90^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-S25km	Southern Lambert Azimuthal	25.0	720	720	$-90^\circ-0^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$
EASE2-S3.125km	Southern Lambert Azimuthal	3.125	5760	5760	$-90^\circ-0^\circ$	$\pm 180^\circ$

B ESCAT Data Definition

B.1 File Requirements

Following Brodzik et al. (2021), *ESCAT* product file requirements include:

- Output file format shall be acceptable for NSIDC DAAC to easily ingest to ECS
- File size maximum will be < 1 GB (larger files are allowed in ECS, but fast network speeds cannot always be assumed)
- Files will conform to netCDF-CF 1.6 conventions for all but the requirement that puts the lat/lon arrays into the file; however, we will include CF-compliant coordinate variables with projected coordinate locations
- Files should pass CF-compliance-checking for all but the lat/lon arrays (we used JPL compliance-checker)
- Each file will contain 1 or more array variables, with associated ancillary variables, possibly different ancillary variables for each gridding technique. We may have a practical limit on the number of ancillary variables to include, limited by maximum file size
- Each file of the same type (GRD or SIR) will contain the same file-level metadata for that type.
- We will follow the DRY (Don't Repeat Yourself) principle: Metadata will not be duplicated at multiple places in the same file
- DRY exception: Time values will be machine- and human-readable
- DRY exception: Some projection metadata may be in multiple forms (a proj4 string and/or a WKT string)
- Variable/attribute names will be CF-compliant whenever possible

The *ESCAT* .nc files work with gdal utility, *gdal_translate*, to produce a geoTIFF version of each of the data variables <variable_name> in the file, (details in Brodzik et al. (2018)), for e.g.:

```
$ gdal_translate -of GTiff -b 1 \
NETCDF:''cetb.nc':<variable_name> variable_name.tif
```

B.2 Filename Convention

ESCAT data are distributed by the NSIDC DAAC (<http://nsidc.org/data/nsidc-TBD>).

Filenames are:

```
<product_id>-<grid_name>-<platform_sensor>-<yyyyddd>
-<channel_id>-<pass>-<algorithm>-<input_source>-<version>.nc
```

where parts of the filename are described in Table 7.

Table 7: ESCAT file naming convention

Part	Description	Values
<product_id>	NSIDC unique data product id	NSIDC-TBD
<grid_name>	EASE-Grid 2.0 grid id	See Table 6
<platform>	Satellite platform	ADEOS
<sensor>	Sensor name	ASCAT
<yyyyddd>	Date	4-digit year and 3-digit day-of-year
<channel_id>	Channel (frequency in GHz and polarization)	5.3VV
<pass>	Pass direction (T grids) or LTOD (N or S grids)	one of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B = Both (all measurements) • A = Ascending • D = Descending • M = Morning • E = Evening
<algorithm>	Reconstruction algorithm	one of GRD, AVE or SIR
<version>	Version number	production version number

B.3 File Content, v1.0

The following is a sample NetCDF *ncdump -h* utility output for a particular ESCAT v1.0 6.25 km SIR file. File-level metadata and processing details vary depending on projection, spatial resolution and processing details (method,ncd etc.).

```
netcdf BYU-ESCAT-EASE2_S6.25km-ERS_ESCAT-1998180_1998197-5.3VV-B-SIR-v1.0 {
dimensions:
time = UNLIMITED ; // (1 currently)
y = 2880 ;
x = 2880 ;
variables:
double time(time) ;
time:standard_name = "time" ;
time:coverage_content_type = "coordinate" ;
time:long_name = "ANSI date" ;
time:units = "days since 1972-01-01 00:00:00" ;
time:calendar = "gregorian" ;
```

```
time:axis = "T" ;
time:valid_range = 0., 1.79769313486232e+308 ;
double y(y) ;
y:standard_name = "projection_y_coordinate" ;
y:coverage_content_type = "coordinate" ;
y:long_name = "y" ;
y:units = "meters" ;
y:axis = "Y" ;
y:valid_range = -9000000., 9000000. ;
double x(x) ;
x:standard_name = "projection_x_coordinate" ;
x:coverage_content_type = "coordinate" ;
x:long_name = "x" ;
x:units = "meters" ;
x:axis = "X" ;
x:valid_range = -9000000., 9000000. ;
char crs ;
crs:grid_mapping_name = "lambert_azimuthal_equal_area" ;
crs:longitude_of_projection_origin = 0. ;
crs:latitude_of_projection_origin = -90. ;
crs:false_easting = 0. ;
crs:false_northing = 0. ;
crs:semi_major_axis = 6378137. ;
crs:inverse_flattening = 298.257223563 ;
crs:proj4text = "+proj=laea +lat_0=-90 +lon_0=0 +x_0=0 +y_0=0 +ellps=WGS84 +datum=WGS84";
crs:srid = "urn:ogc:def:crs:EPSG::6932" ;
crs:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
crs:references = "[\"EASE-Grid 2.0 documentation: http://nsidc.org/data/ease/ease\_grid2\"";
crs:crs_wkt = "PROJCRS[\"WGS 84 / NSIDC EASE-Grid 2.0 South\", BASEGEODCRS[\"WGS 84\", D";
crs:long_name = "EASE2_S6.25km" ;
short Sigma0_ave(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_ave:standard_name = "brightness_temperature" ;
Sigma0_ave:long_name = "SIR Sigma0" ;
Sigma0_ave:units = "1" ;
Sigma0_ave:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_ave:valid_range = 0s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_ave:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_ave:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_offset";
Sigma0_ave:scale_factor = 0.002f ;
Sigma0_ave:add_offset = -55.f ;
```

```
Sigma0_ave:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_ave:coverage_content_type = "image" ;
short Sigma0_slope_ave(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:standard_name = "brightness_temperature" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:long_name = "SIR Sigma0 slope" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:units = "1" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:valid_range = 0s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_
Sigma0_slope_ave:scale_factor = 0.001f ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:add_offset = -2.f ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_slope_ave:coverage_content_type = "image" ;
short Sigma0(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0:standard_name = "brightness_temperature" ;
Sigma0:long_name = "SIR Sigma0" ;
Sigma0:units = "1" ;
Sigma0:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0:valid_range = 0s, 32767s ;
Sigma0:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_offset" ;
Sigma0:scale_factor = 0.002f ;
Sigma0:add_offset = -55.f ;
Sigma0:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0:coverage_content_type = "image" ;
Sigma0:sir_number_of_iterations = 30 ;
Sigma0:median_filter = 1 ;
Sigma0:temporal_division = "Both" ;
Sigma0:temporal_division_local_start_time = 5.f ;
Sigma0:temporal_division_local_end_time = 17.f ;
Sigma0:frequency_and_polarization = "5.3VV" ;
short Sigma0_slope(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_slope:standard_name = "brightness_temperature" ;
Sigma0_slope:long_name = "SIR Sigma0 slope" ;
Sigma0_slope:units = "1" ;
Sigma0_slope:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_slope:valid_range = 0s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_slope:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_slope:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_offs
```

```
Sigma0_slope:scale_factor = 0.001f ;
Sigma0_slope:add_offset = -2.f ;
Sigma0_slope:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_slope:coverage_content_type = "image" ;
short Sigma0_num_samples(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_num_samples:long_name = "SIR Number of Measurements" ;
Sigma0_num_samples:units = "count" ;
Sigma0_num_samples:_FillValue = 0s ;
Sigma0_num_samples:valid_range = 1s, 255s ;
Sigma0_num_samples:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_num_samples:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
short Incidence_angle(time, y, x) ;
Incidence_angle:standard_name = "angle_of_incidence" ;
Incidence_angle:long_name = "SIR Incidence Angle" ;
Incidence_angle:units = "degree" ;
Incidence_angle:_FillValue = -1s ;
Incidence_angle:valid_range = 0s, 9000s ;
Incidence_angle:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Incidence_angle:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_o
Incidence_angle:scale_factor = 0.01f ;
Incidence_angle:add_offset = 0.f ;
Incidence_angle:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Incidence_angle:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
short Sigma0_std_dev(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_std_dev:long_name = "SIR Sigma0 standard deviation" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:units = "1" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_std_dev:valid_range = -32766s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_std_dev:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_of
Sigma0_std_dev:scale_factor = 0.002f ;
Sigma0_std_dev:add_offset = 0.f ;
Sigma0_std_dev:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_std_dev:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
short Sigma0_time(time, y, x) ;
Sigma0_time:long_name = "Time of Day" ;
Sigma0_time:units = "minutes since 1998-06-29 00:00:00" ;
Sigma0_time:_FillValue = -32768s ;
Sigma0_time:valid_range = -32767s, 32767s ;
Sigma0_time:packing_convention = "netCDF" ;
```

```
Sigma0_time:packing_convention_description = "unpacked = scale_factor*packed + add_offset" ;
Sigma0_time:scale_factor = 1.f ;
Sigma0_time:add_offset = 0.f ;
Sigma0_time:grid_mapping = "crs" ;
Sigma0_time:coverage_content_type = "auxiliaryInformation" ;
Sigma0_time:calendar = "gregorian" ;

// global attributes:
:references = "Early, D. S., and D.G. Long. 2001. Image Reconstruction and Enhanced Resolution Scatterometry of the Earth's Surface Using Synthetic Aperture Radar" ;
:title = "ESCAT Enhanced Resolution EASE-Grid 2.0 Sigma0" ;
:id = "doi:TBD" ;
:summary = "Enhanced-resolution, gridded ERS scatterometer C-band radar backscatter" ;
:project = "Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder" ;
:contributor_name = "David G. Long, NASA Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder" ;
:contributor_role = "Principal Investigator and Developer, Data Producer" ;
:citation = "D. G. Long\nESCAT Enhanced-Resolution EASE-Grid 2.0 Sigma0.\nVersion 1.0.\n" ;
:license = "These data are freely, openly, and fully available to use without restriction" ;
:Conventions = "CF-1.6, ACDD-1.3" ;
:product_version = "v1.0" ;
:software_version_id = "BYU03.00" ;
:software_repository = "" ;
:history = "ers_cetb_sir" ;
:comment = "Epoch date for data in this file: 1998-06-29 00:00:00Z" ;
:source = ": See input_fileN list and number_of_input_files attributes" ;
:metadata_link = "http://www.scp.byu.edu/" ;
:institution = "Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder\nElectrical and Computer Engineering Department" ;
:publisher_name = "Scatterometer Climate Record Pathfinder" ;
:publisher_type = "institution" ;
:publisher_url = "http://www.scp.byu.edu" ;
:publisher_email = "long@ee.byu.edu" ;
:program = "NASA Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS)" ;
:standard_name_vocabulary = "CF Standard Name Table (v27, 28 September 2013)" ;
:cdm_data_type = "Grid" ;
:keywords = "EARTH SCIENCE > SPECTRAL/ENGINEERING > MICROWAVE > RADAR BACKSCATTER" ;
:keywords_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Earth Science Keyword Table" ;
:platform = "ERS > Earth Remote Sensing" ;
:platform_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Earth Science Keyword Table" ;
:instrument = "ESCAT C-BAND RADAR > ESCAT C-Band Radar" ;
:instrument_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Earth Science Keyword Table" ;
:time_coverage_resolution = "P1d" ;
```

```
:geospatial_bounds = "" ;
:geospatial_bounds_crs = "" ;
:geospatial_lat_min = -90. ;
:geospatial_lat_max = 0. ;
:geospatial_lon_min = -180. ;
:geospatial_lon_max = 180. ;
:geospatial_x_units = "meters" ;
:geospatial_y_units = "meters" ;
:naming_authority = "org.doi.dx" ;
:date_created = "2024-12-24T17:45:48GMT" ;
:date_modified = "2024-12-24T17:45:48GMT" ;
:date_issued = "2024-12-24T17:45:48GMT" ;
:date_metadata_modified = "2024-12-24T17:45:48GMT" ;
:input_data_quality_filtering = "Only used highest-quality input data." ;
:acknowledgement = "This data set was created with funding from NASA Grant #TBD." ;
:processing_level = "Level 3" ;
:creator_name = "David Long" ;
:creator_type = "person" ;
:creator_email = "long@ee.byu.edu" ;
:creator_url = "http://www.scp.byu.edu" ;
:creator_institution = "Electrical and Computer Engineering Department\nBrigham Young Un
:geospatial_lat_units = "degrees_north" ;
:geospatial_lon_units = "degrees_east" ;
:geospatial_x_resolution = "6250.00 meters" ;
:geospatial_y_resolution = "6250.00 meters" ;
:time_coverage_start = "1998-06-28T23:59:00.00Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "1998-07-02T00:42:00.00Z" ;
:time_coverage_duration = "P03T00:43:00.00" ;
}
```